

The Peace Of Space Theory

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Abstract - The theory The Peace Of Space Theory is about the Einstein's theory Of special relativity which he published in 1905. This theory tells about the limitations Of the "Theory of special relativity". This theory tells if we imagine about a planet which is 179 trillion light years away from Earth and its active gravitational field by which it easily attract the objects is $4.8 \cdot 10^{14}$ meter and its gravitational acceleration is 250 m/s^2 . If we put these values in third equation of motion then we found that the Einstein's Theory of special relativity got failed.

Key Words: optics, photonics, light, lasers, templates, journals

1. INTRODUCTION

This theory is based on a special topic discovered by the world's greatest physicist Albert Einstein in 1905 his theory of special relativity. This theory "The Peace Of Space Theory" tells that, how Einstein's is not complete in its own there are some limitations of his theory and how it can be break using laws of physics.

The peace of space theory. As we know that in 1905 Einstein published a research paper about his theory of special relativity in this theory I am going to consulted about it there is some limitation of this theory as we know that as vast the universe is spread from galaxy to galaxy there is no limitation of universe and galaxies so we can assume about a planet which is 189 trillion light years away from the Earth if we consider it's gravitational acceleration be $250 \text{ m per second square}$ and its gravitational field by which it easily attract the object to its surface area is $4.8 \cdot 10^{14}$ meter then if you drop a object from $4.5 \cdot 10^{14}$ meter from its surface then if you put these values in third equation of motion then we find out Einstein theory of special relativity got failed, beside this Einstein never expose about the source by which the object's mass become infinite and as we know that mass cannot be created but it can be transformed from energy to the mass but Einstein not clarify about the source by which the big amount of energy converted into mass which is infinite and that amount of energy is unmeasurable which is more than that energy which is used to accelerate the object Of infinite mass.

Mathematical expression Of the theory. According to previous consult the gravitational acceleration of the planet is 250 m/s^2 and its gravitational field by which it easily attract the object is $4.8 \cdot 10^{14}$ meter and from where we drop the object is $4.5 \cdot 10^{14}$ from its surface and when we drop any object then its initial velocity is zero. Put this values in the below equation- $[V^2=u^2+2as]$ Then $V^2=0^2+2as$. Then,

$V=474341649 \text{ m/s}$ approximately which is greater than speed of light- Not only it if I will get the right equipment and support then I will prove it experimentally also now.

2. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of this theory after the observing and consulting deeply, we can conclude that Einstein's "Theory of special relativity" has some limitations and got failed in its speed limit barrier that is speed Of light using the concept of physics.

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REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHIES

I am called Dhruv Singh Sonkar (born on November 27,
2008 in India
,U.P, Unnao, Purwa (town), Durgapur) studying in 11th
standard from science stream entrepreneur in physics and
mathematics.Re cently discovered some mathematical theories.
Prepared models of some devices which I will invent as soon I
get required equipments (some of them are wireless
electricity,Space craft which can travel more than speed of
light, Permanent mobile battery and time travelling machine.